

An Overview of the Global Financial Crisis and Islamic Finance: Is Islamic Finance a Viable Alternative?

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The severity of the global financial crisis has shaken the foundations of the capitalist financial system and lead to a search for alternative ideas and solutions. Many authors have identified the Islamic financial system, based on the teachings of Shari'ah (Islamic Law), as a viable alternative that can offer a cure to the current financial deceases. The main objective of this paper is to critically review the viability of Islamic finance as an alternative financial system. In order to do so, an overview of Islamic financial system, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* (Objectives of the Shari'ah), the core values of Islamic financial system and its most commonly used financial instruments is carried out. At the same time, an attempt is made to establish a relationship between the global financial crisis and Islamic financial system by highlighting similar features between the two that may undermine the stability of Islamic financial system in the future. It is argued that the underlying principles protected Islamic financial system from the negative effects of the global financial crisis. This paper claims that, in fact, the infancy and underdevelopment of Islamic financial system were the main reasons that 'relatively' saved Islamic financial system from the negative effects of the global financial crisis. Furthermore, as Islamic financial products are frequently imitations of the conventional financial products engineered by stitching together a composite of Islamic contracts, they are likely to share the same economic fate in the end.

Key words: Islamic finance, Islamic Financial System (IFS), Shari'ah (Islamic law), *maqasid al-Shari'ah*, global financial crisis (GFC),

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INTRODUCTION

The global financial crisis (GFC) of 2008-09, considered to be the worst crisis since the Great Depression, revealed a wide range of issues concerning the stability and soundness of the current financial system. As a result, the international community started a serious re-examination of the existing international financial architecture and discussed regulatory reforms. At the same time, a search is underway for a more enduring solution.

Despite the turbulent environment caused by the GFC, the global expansion of Islamic finance has continued, and its development has remained dynamic. In fact, Islamic finance has become one of the fastest growing financial segments in the international financial system, and it is internationally recognized and accepted by all communities as a competitive and robust form of financial intermediation. Today, Islamic finance attracts both Muslim and non-Muslim market participants. Its worldwide market share has increased tremendously and is estimated to be between US\$800 billion and US\$1 trillion. In fact, according to International Financial Services London (IFSL), the Islamic financial industry (IFI) is growing at 15-20 per cent per annum—a growth rate that far exceeds that of the conventional financial industry (KFH Research, 2009; McKenzie, 2010, January).

The main objective of this paper is to provide an overview of the IFS and its underlying principles in light of the GFC. This paper is based on an extensive literature review of the GFC and the IFS. Section Two briefly reviews the GFC: what went wrong and how the current crisis evolved into a global meltdown. Due to space limitations, we are not able to go into a detailed discussion of the GFC. Thus, the objective here is not to sort out all the problems or to suggest solutions, but rather to highlight the problems within

the current financial system. Based on that analysis, we can relate the major flaws of the current financial system to the future development of IFI.

This is followed by a concise summary of the IFS, its historic development and current state in Section Three. Since *maqasid al-Shari'ah* (objectives of the Shari'ah) form a foundation of the IFS, it is necessary for us to outline their key concepts in Section Four. The IFS is a form of financial intermediation that incorporates several salient features which guide the process of mobilizing and allocating funds to generate productive economic activity. As such, it is important to understand the underlying principles on which it is based. Hence, the salient features of and basic modes of financing within the IFS are discussed in Sections Five and Six, respectively. Section Seven briefly summarizes the effects of the GFC on IFI. Finally, Section Eight consists of concluding remarks.

THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL MELTDOWN: A BRIEF REVIEW

In the last 27 years or so, the world has witnessed more than 124 distinct financial crises. Leading economists call the current global financial crisis the most severe and the worst crisis since the Great Depression (for example see Jones, 2009; Nonomiya & Lanman, 2008; NY Times, 2010, January 12; Volcker, 2010). The crisis has shaken the very foundations of the capitalist financial system, and there is a growing demand for a new system or a restructuring of the current financial architecture.

The financial crisis initially started with the collapse of the sub-prime¹ mortgage market in 2007, mainly due to excessive and imprudent credit growth (*Islamic Finance and Global Financial Stability*, April 2010; Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009, p. 23). For example, in 2006 alone, lenders made \$640 billion in subprime loans, which amounted to about 20% of all mortgage lending and about 17% of home purchases in the same year (CNNMoney.com, 2007).

One of the main causes of the collapse of the sub-prime mortgage market was a sharp fall in mortgage prices that led to the burst of the housing bubble. Economic conditions worsened throughout 2007 and 2008. Nevertheless, many authors are of the opinion that the crisis started much earlier and that previous crises had a major role to play in the current global financial crisis (See Mizen, 2008; NY Times, 2010, January 12; Oxlade, 2010; Wang & Wen, 2009, July).

Other factors that contributed to the crisis were: the interest-based and debt-driven financial system, monetary policy and a prolonged period of low interest rates, complex and opaque products, mispricing of risks, liquidity, leveraging, greed and predatory lending practices, lax regulation and supervision—to name just a few (Cooper, 2008; FSF, 2008; Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009; OECD, 2009a, 2009b; Taylor, 2008, November). All of this encouraged rapid and substantial growth of credit and, as a result, pushed house prices up. For example, in 2001 the Federal Reserve cut the interest rate from 6.5% to 1.75%, and even further, to 1%, in 2003; a 45-year low (Nonomiya & Lanman, 2008).

¹ A subprime mortgage refers to a home loan made to a borrower who does not qualify for a “prime” loan because he or she has a blemished or non-existent credit history. These loans are referred to as “Ninja loans” - no income, no jobs, and no assets. (See Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009, p. 23; Russell, n.d.)

During the same period, in a furious search for yield, the banks and other financial institutions resorted to widespread financial engineering and innovations. Some of the products they came up with were mortgage-backed securities (MBSs), collateralized debt obligations (CDOs), and credit default swaps (CDSs). Most of these products derived their value mainly from mortgage payments and rising housing prices. As a result, they were positively correlated with the movement of prices in the mortgage market.

Prices in the mortgage market, up until 2006, were skyrocketing. In the following three years, prices fell by more than 30 percent. On the other hand, the Fed raised interest rates from 1.25% in May 2004 to 5.25% in May 2006, indicating an end of the low-interest-rate regime (Jones, 2009). This sharp rise in the interest rate made payments difficult for subprime borrowers, and defaults on payments began. Similarly, borrowing decreased due to the increase in the cost, causing the prices in the mortgage market to fall. The decline in house prices reduced the value of MBSs and other derivative instruments. This, in turn, had a further effect on the initial borrowers, who were relying on the value of the properties and on the financial institutions' solvency to validate their highly leveraged assets.

Contagion of this crisis reached Europe and the rest of the world almost instantly as the interbank market seized to function. For example, in UK, Northern Rock was hit by the crisis in September 2007 and in February 2008 it was nationalized (Croft & Giles, 2008; Oxlade, 2010). Similarly, banks in Germany were hard hit by the credit crisis. IKB Deutsche Industriebank, affected by losses related to the US subprime market, was rescued by a government-led bailout in August 2007. At the same time, Landesbank Baden-Württemberg (LBBW), the German public-sector bank, bailed out the troubled

Sachsen LB (Simensen, 2007; Simensen & Benoit, 2007). BNP Paribas, France's biggest bank, was so badly hit by the U.S. subprime mortgage crisis that it decided to halt withdrawals from three investment funds (Boyd, 2007).

Faced with these complex problems, governments all over the world began pumping money into credit markets and started bailing out “too big to fail” institutions. The U.S. Treasury sponsored its Troubled Asset Relief Plan (TARP) and the Fed stands ready to provide funds as necessary to keep the financial system functioning smoothly. In fact, central banks in Europe, Asia, and the Americas injected trillions of dollars in order to save the financial market from what George Soros called “cardiac arrest” (Mirakhor & Krichene, 2009, p. 28).

All of these measures were only partially and artificially successful and despite all the governmental efforts, the banks are reluctant to lend. Bloomberg reported that by February 2009 the U.S. government had pledged more than \$11.6 trillion (For details see Pittman & Ivry, 2009; Shah, 2009).

THE ISLAMIC FINANCIAL SYSTEM: AN OVERVIEW

The Islamic finance broadly refers to financial activities that are guided by the teachings of the Shari‘ah (Islamic law).² The primary sources of Shari‘ah are the Holy Qur’an and the Sunnah,³ which are followed by the consensus of the jurists (*ijma’*) and analogy (*qiyas*). Shari‘ah strictly prohibits the payment and receipt of interest. However, describing the IFS simply as “interest-free” does not reflect a true and holistic picture of

² Literally, Shari‘ah means a path to a watering-place, a clear path to be followed. This led to its use for the path which the believer has to tread in order to obtain guidance in this world and deliverance in the next.

³ *Sunnah* is an Arabic word that means ‘habit’ or ‘usual practice’. Technically, this term refers to whatever was reported that the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings be upon him) said, did, or gave his tacit approval.

the system (Iqbal, 1997). Islam in general and Islamic finance in particular, strives for preservation of property rights, emphasizing ethical standards, sharing of risks, and promoting social justice (Askari, Iqbal, & Mirakhor, 2010; Shanmugam & Zahari, 2009). Moreover, not only must investment activities be in line with the ethical principles of the Shari‘ah, they should also take into consideration public interests (*masalih* pl. of *maslahah*).

The principles of Islamic finance have been practiced in the Muslim world down through the ages. The term “Islamic financial system” is relatively new and was coined only in the mid-1980s (Iqbal, 1997; Zaher & Hassan, 2001). Nevertheless, since its inception some forty years ago, and especially in the last decade, the IFI has evolved into a respectable and essential part of the international financial system. As a result, IFI now encompasses banking, insurance and capital markets (*Islamic Finance and Global Financial Stability*, April 2010).

Although Islamic financial instruments were used throughout the ages, the first experiments with Islamic banks came much later, in the 1960s and 1970s.⁴ Mit Ghamr Local Savings Bank, established in Egypt in 1963, is considered the first Islamic bank. Following the success of Mit Ghamr, in 1967 the Nasir Social Bank was established and it was the first social bank operating in line with Shari‘ah principles (Venardos, 2005). Table 1 below shows the historical development of Islamic banking and finance.

[TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE]

⁴ Some studies showed that the first Muslim-owned banks were established in the 1920s and 1930s. However, these banks adopted practices similar to conventional banks. Later on, in the 1940s and the 1950s, Malaysia and Pakistan initiated several experiments with small Islamic banks. For more details see Venardos (2005, pp. 4-5).

Today, Islamic finance attracts both Muslim and non-Muslim market participants. The worldwide market for Shari‘ah-compliant Islamic financial products is estimated to be between US \$800 billion and \$1 trillion. According to London-based IFSL (McKenzie, 2010, January), Shari‘ah-compliant assets grew to \$951bn by the end of 2008, up 25% from \$758bn in 2007, and up about 75% from \$549bn in 2006 (see Chart 1 below) (see also KFH Research, 2009). IFI is growing at 15-20 per cent per annum—a growth rate that far exceeds that of the conventional financial industry.

According to *Islamic Banker*, there are two models of Islamic finance today. First, there is a systematic approach to Islamic finance as implemented by Malaysia and its dual-banking model. In this model, conventional and Islamic finance operate side-by-side with separate (yet similar) rules and regulations governing them.

Second, there is the “ad hoc approach”, *Islamic Banker* further claims, “where neither the government nor the regulator even acknowledge the need for a stand-alone Islamic banking and regulatory framework, let alone enabling laws” (Islamic Banker, 2010, p. 2).

[CHART 1 ABOUT HERE]

***Maqasid al-Shari'ah* (objectives of the Shari'ah)**

Maqasid al-Shari'ah (objectives of the Shari‘ah, sometimes known as *maslahah*⁵ or public interest) is a vast topic that goes beyond the scope of this paper. Here we would just like to draw attention to this subject, as it is often argued that the objectives or *maqasid al-Shari'ah* are the starting point of Islamic economics. Islamic finance in particular and Islamic economics in general are supposed to be based on the *maslahah*

⁵ The Holy Qur'an is full of references to *maslahah* (benefits). For example, see: (57:25), (16:90), (2:151), (3:164), (2:185), (22:78), (2:286), (4:28), (27:77).

prescribed by *maqasid al-Shari'ah*. Economic agents in an Islamic framework, “will seek *maslahah* instead of seeking utility in the conventional sense” (Khan, 2002, p. 63).

Due attention to this topic was given only in the eleventh century by al-Ghazali (505H/1111 CE) and later on by al-Shatibi (d.790/1388) (Kamali, 2008, p. 124). According to Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyyah (d. 1356), Shari'ah aims at safeguarding people's interest in this world and the Hereafter (Ibn Qayyim, n.d., p. 1; see also Kamali, 2008, p. 27). Referring to the *maqasid al-Shari'ah*, al-Ghazali said: “The objective of the Shari'ah is to promote the welfare of human beings, which lies in safeguarding their faith, their life, their intellect, their posterity, and their wealth. Whatever ensures the safeguard of these five fundamentals serves public interest and is desirable” (Al-Ghazali, 1356/1937, pp. 139-140; see also Chapra, 1998, pp. 99-114).

Although there are different classifications of *maqasid al-Shari'ah*, Muslim scholars classified them into three main categories: *daruriyyat* (essentials), *hajiyyat* (needs) and *tahsiniyyat* (embellishments).⁶ *Maslahah*, according to *'ulama*, refers to “the preservation of the objectives of Shari'ah,” (Khan, 2002, p. 64) which is considered to be the main objective of the Shari'ah (Kamali, 1998, p. 1). The essential *masalih* (plural of *maslahah*) or *daruriyyat* are divided into five (Al-Ghazali, 1356/1937; see also Ayub, 2007, pp. 22-25; Kamali, 1998, p. 2; Khan, 2002, p. 64):

- a) Preservation of faith/religion (*Din*)
- b) Preservation of the life (*Nafs*)
- c) Preservation of lineage/descendants/procreation (*Nasl*)

⁶ For detailed discussion on different classifications see Ibn Ashur, 2001-1421AH, pp. 112-129; Kamali, 1998; 2008, p. 134.

- d) Preservation of property (*Mal*)
- e) Preservation of intellect/reason (*'Aql*)

Salient features of Islamic finance

Many authors have discussed the basic principles of Islamic finance (Askari, Iqbal, Mirakhor, & Krichenne, 2010; Ayub, 2007; DIFC, 2007, December; El-Gamal, 2006; *Islamic Finance and Global Financial Stability*, April 2010; Venardos, 2005; Visser, 2009). They are primarily derived from the Qur'an, Sunnah, *ijma'*, and *qiyas*. The most important are:⁷

- i. **Prohibition of *Riba* (interest or usury):**⁸ Payment and receipt of interest (*riba*) are prohibited in Islam. In this regard, the Qur'an says: "*Those who devour usury (riba) will not stand except as one stands whom Satan has driven mad by his touch. That is because they say, 'Trade is like riba,' whereas Allah has permitted trade and forbidden riba.*"⁹ The literal meaning of *riba* is 'excess', 'growth' or 'increment.' Technically, it refers to a predetermined interest collected by a lender, which the lender receives over and above the principal amount he has lent out. *Riba* is further classified into two types:

1. *Riba al-fadl*. This largely applies to barter transactions. It refers to the trading of one commodity of a category to which the rules of *riba* apply for another

⁷ For detailed discussion on basic principles of Islamic financial system please see: (Askari, Iqbal, & Mirakhor, 2010; Ayub, 2007; Shanmugam & Zahari, 2009; Usmani, 2002; Venardos, 2005; Vogel & Hayes, 1998).

⁸ Some authors differentiate between usury and interest and say that *riba* refers to usury only while interest is not included in the prohibition. In this paper, the term *riba* refers to both interest and usury. For detailed discussion on the issue of *riba*, see: (Al-Zuhayli, 2003b, p. 309)

⁹ Al-Qur'an, 2:275. In fact, the receipt of *riba* is forbidden in the Holy Qur'an, while the payment of *riba* is prohibited in the Sunnah of the Prophet (peace be upon him), and consensus (*ijma'*). In the Qur'an, the strongest prohibition is provided in the verses [2:275-279].

commodity of the same category, with an increase of one compensation over the other (Al-Zuhayli, 2003b, p. 312).¹⁰

2. *Riba al-nasi'ah* is specific to loans. It refers to any excess paid over the principal amount as a compensation for a delay in repayment.

- ii. **Prohibition of *Gharar* (excessive risk & uncertainty):** Literally, the term *gharar* refers to something with a pleasant appearance and unpleasant reality (Al-Darir, 1995, p. 48). Consequently, the *gharar* can be defined as the sale of probable goods whose existence and/or characteristics are not certain. Due to these reasons this trade is akin to gambling. Examples of *gharar* are the sale of fish in the sea, of birds in the sky, and of unripe fruits on the tree, which cause excessive and avoidable uncertainty.
- iii. **Prohibition of *Maysir* (gambling/speculation):** Islam prohibits gambling and games of chance in which there is a possibility of total loss to one party. It is a zero-sum game whereby there is a transfer of wealth from one party to another without creating any new wealth. One of the reasons for prohibiting *maysir* (gambling) is that it invokes enmity and distracts the faithful from worshiping.¹¹
- iv. **Shari'ah-compliant Activities:** Islamic financial institutions may engage in or finance only activities that are in line with teachings of Shari'ah. As a result, financing casino activities as well as the production of tobacco, alcohol, pork, pornography, weapons, among others, are strictly disallowed.

¹⁰ The following items are mentioned in a *hadith* to be *ribawi* and as such should be exchanged only in an equal measure or quantity: gold, silver, barley, wheat, salt and dates.

¹¹ Gambling is prohibited in the Qur'an [5:90-91].

- v. **Risk-and-Return Sharing:** While the Shari‘ah prohibits earning income through charging interest, it permits income generation through the sharing of risks and rewards between the parties. In other words, Islam encourages and promotes entrepreneurship that builds trust and cooperation between partners.
- vi. **Sanctity of Contracts:** Fulfilling contractual obligations in Islam is considered a sacred duty.¹² Furthermore, disclosure of full information is also required in order to reduce the risk of asymmetric information and moral hazard.
- vii. **Social Justice:** Islam prohibits any transaction that leads to injustice and exploitation. Moreover, Islam gives preference to public interest over individual interest.

By prohibiting *riba*, *gharar* and *maysir* on the one side, and promoting risk-and-return sharing, cooperation and *maslahah* on the other, Islam seeks to foster an environment based on fairness and justice. In short, the focus of Islamic finance is on community banking, ethical banking, and socially responsible investing.

Basic modes of Islamic finance

The range of Islamic financial instruments has broadened considerably since the inception of IFI. There are various instruments that can be used in different sectors such as housing projects, financing car purchases, financing working materials and

¹² Refer to Qur’an, [5:1] where it says: “O you who believe! Fulfill (all) obligations.”

equipments, financing business projects, government deficits, etc. The following is a brief explanation of basic modes of finance applicable in IFI:¹³

Qard Hasan (benevolent loan) literally means “good loan.” Technically, it is a contract of loan between two parties on the basis of social welfare. The amount of repayment must be equal to the amount borrowed. However, it is allowed for a borrower to pay more than the amount borrowed as long as it is not stated or agreed at the beginning of the contract.

Musharakah (active partnership) literally means “sharing” and refers to a profit-and-loss-sharing partnership between two or more parties. It is akin to a joint venture arrangement. In this case, all parties contribute capital, either in the form of cash or in kind, and labor. Any profit derived from the venture will be shared based on a pre-agreed profit-sharing ratio, but a loss will be shared based on capital contribution.

Musharakah Mutanaqisah (diminishing partnership) is a hybrid financing technique involving both *musharakah* and *ijarah*. It is a contract between a financier (bank) and a beneficiary (client) in which the two agree to jointly own an asset or property with a condition that the financier will gradually sell his shares to the beneficiary at an agreed price and in accordance with an agreed schedule.

Mudarabah (passive partnership) is a special type of partnership between a capital owner (*rabb al-mal*), who contributes capital, and an entrepreneur or manager (*mudarib*), who runs the business. Any profit generated is distributed according to a pre-agreed ratio, but the capital itself cannot be guaranteed. However, if there is a loss, it will be

¹³ For a detailed discussion of the basic modes of Islamic finance, please see: (Al-Zuhayli, 2003a, 2003b; Ayub, 2007; ISRA, 2011; Kahf, 1998; Shanmugam & Zahari, 2009; Usmani, 2002; Venardos, 2005; Zaher & Hassan, 2001).

borne by the provider of capital, who has no control over the management of the business.

Bay' al-Murabahah (cost-plus financing)¹⁴ refers to a contract of sale and purchase of asset whereby the cost and profit margin (mark-up) are made known to the customer (buyer). In this case, the bank will purchase the asset from the supplier as requested by the client and will sell it to the client at cost plus mark-up price. The selling price is predetermined at the beginning of the contract and cannot be changed afterward.

Bay' al-Salam (future delivery) is a sale contract in which the price is paid on the spot but the delivery of goods purchased will be deferred to a specified future date.

Ijarah (leasing) literally means 'to give something on rent.' It is a contract whereby a lessor (bank or owner) leases out an underlying asset to a lessee at an agreed lease rental for a predetermined lease period. The ownership of the leased asset always remains with the lessor, who is also responsible for its maintenance.

Ijarah wa Iqtina (lease ending in ownership)¹⁵ is similar to an *ijarah* contract. The only difference is that at the end of the contract the ownership of the leased asset is transferred to the lessee. This transfer of ownership is made through a new contract, in which the leased asset is either given to the lessee as a gift or is sold to him at a nominal price at the end of the lease agreement.

Istisna' (commissioned manufacture) refers to a purchase-order contract where a buyer requires a seller to deliver a completed asset in the future according to the specifications stated in the agreement.

¹⁴ Also known as *al-murabahah lil-amr bi al-shira* (*Murabahah* for the Purchase Orderer).

¹⁵ It is also known as *Ijarah Thumma al-Bay'* or *Ijarah Muntahiyah bi-Tamlik*.

Sukuk (Islamic certificate/bond) is a document or certificate that represents the value of a diffused share in ownership of tangible assets of a particular project or a specific investment activity, usufruct or services. It is similar to a conventional bond in that it can be traded in the stock market. However, it is usually an asset-backed bond, which is structured in accordance with the Shari‘ah.

THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS AND THE ISLAMIC FINANCE

By now there are many papers, studies, reports, statements and books about the GFC, and many “solutions” have been (at least in theory) suggested. Nevertheless, all these solutions came from ‘within the box’ and are biased towards the financial system itself. The very same people and corporations that brought about this crisis in the first place are the same people and corporations that are called upon, backed by the government(s), to rescue us. It is hard to believe that they can offer us anything but another miserable end result.

Thus, running up a huge fiscal deficit by the US government and many other governments around the world; bringing another set of rules and regulations; introducing yet another regulator when there are already 115 regulators in the USA; cutting the pay slips of the Wall Street executives on one side while allowing them to cash in huge bonuses on the other are counterproductive measures, as they leave the current—inherently unstable—financial system intact. In other words, we are still stuck with the financial system the way it was functioning prior to the crisis, and if we continue operating under this system we are running a great risk of another crisis (or rather crises) in the near future.

On the other hand, when this crisis unfolded, many rushed to conclude that Islamic finance is better suited to fend off the negative effects of the global crisis. They also went on saying that Islamic finance is a better alternative to the global financial architecture without realizing the inherent positive relationship between conventional and Islamic finance. The author believes that, although the underlying documents are “Shari’ah-compliant,” the *modus operandi*, functions, goals and effects of these “Shari’ah-compliant” products, at the end of the day, share the same features and faith of their conventional counterparties.

The reasons for these claims are manifold, but we would like to highlight only a few here. First, Shari’ah-compliant financial products are nothing more than ‘copycats’ of conventional products (Ahmed, 2009, p. 28).¹⁶ Thus, as mentioned above, although the underlying products (*murabahah*, *ijarah*, *musharakah*, etc.) identified in the documents that are signed between a bank and a customer, these products follow in the footsteps of the conventional products. Islamic economics, as pointed out by one author, “failed to escape the centripetal pull of Western economic thought, and has in many regards been caught in the intellectual web of the very system it set out to replace.”¹⁷ Second, the pricing of these products is done applying conventional formulas with the interest rate as a benchmark. As a result, changes in the interest rate (although not directly stated and present in a Shari’ah-compliant structure) do affect Islamic financial products, and in case of fixed sale products, such as *murabahah* or BBA, this can be disastrous. Third, those involved in Islamic finance in general and Islamic banking in particular took the word ‘banking’ and the features and functions of banks—as understood by the

¹⁶ For details on how this approach will lead to a convergence of the Islamic finance towards the conventional finance please see: (Smolo, 2010).

¹⁷ Also the author here refers to Islamic economics in general, this statement is even more relevant to Islamic finance. See (Nasr, 1991, p. 388).

conventional finance—for granted. A core business of banks—from the conventional point of view—is to borrow low and lend high, making a profit on difference between the two. Hence, the natural question would be: Can we have an Islamic banking? If we define banks in the way mentioned above and as understood by a layman, then my answer would be simple: No! This is because if we are to implement the true Shari’ah-compliant finance, then we are no longer talking about the banking we all know. To put it differently, the nature, activities, features and functions of these—the true Shari’ah-compliant—banks should be fundamentally altered. Fourth, over the years, the Islamic finance developed many products and entered into a fast lane of devising new instruments for capital market, including derivatives. While it is partially true that Islamic finance was in better position during the financial crisis due to its fundamental principles, it is a greater truth that it was better off due to its infancy and underdevelopment when compared to the conventional finance. Fifth, even if we accept Islamic finance as it is now, there are many unresolved issues that are far less developed compared to conventional finance. For example, IF lacks the skilled human capital necessary for future development; the regulation, transparency and supervision of IF is far from satisfactory; not enough attention is given to the issue of standardization and/or harmonization of practices—to name just a few (Smolo, 2009).

Having said all of the above, the author believes that conventional finance is inherently unstable and all of the measures currently being applied to correct it are not bearing the intended fruits. The financial reforms, that are taking place all over the world, do not address the root problems of the financial system. Radical times require radical changes and, according to Kotlikoff, we have come to the point when we have to make this radical change (Kotlikoff, 2010). Kotlikoff intelligently elaborates not only the

inherently destructive nature of the current global financial system, but also offers a viable, yet simple, alternative that addresses all the issues raised by other authors. His remedy is embodied in his idea of Limited Purpose Banking (LPB).¹⁸

Within the same line of argument, many authors pointed out that Islamic finance needs to be reshaped in order to reflect the true nature of Islamic finance as envisioned by pioneers of the Islamic finance. Hence, there might be a need to develop some sort of LPB whereby the tasks and responsibilities of banks are clearly spelled out. The nature of Islamic banks has to be fundamentally changed to reflect the true spirit of Islam and to avoid the pitfalls of conventional finance. In short, the role of the debt-based instruments has to be somehow limited and/or minimized; equity-based instruments should be promoted; and the Islamic finance industry needs a system-wide restructuring.¹⁹

CONCLUSION

The global financial crisis that shook the financial world brought Islamic finance into the limelight as an alternative to the mainstream conventional finance. The true reason for IFI's insulation from the crisis lies, partially, in the fundamental prohibitions of the Shari'ah against *riba*, *gharar*, and *maysir*, and more on the infancy and underdevelopment of the industry.

Finally, the question may be raised: Is Islamic finance a real, stable and viable alternative to the failed (but still living on life support) conventional finance? Based on the

¹⁸ To discuss in detail Kotlikoff's proposal of LPB would require a lot of space and time, and it goes far beyond the scope of this paper. The details are eloquently discussed in his book.

¹⁹ A number of authors are calling for more equity-based finance or at least to make a level-playing field between debt- and equity-based instruments as right now there a sort of preferential treatment for debt. For some suggestions and recommendations see: (Haneef & Smolo, 2010; Iqbal & Mirakhor, 2007; Mirakhor, 2009; Smolo & Mirakhor, 2010).

discussion above and the present state of Islamic finance, the Islamic finance industry is driving down the same road as its stepmother, conventional finance. The only difference between the two is that Islamic finance lags behind the conventional finance. In other words, it is just a matter of time when we will be faced with the same problems as conventional finance faces today.

It is believed, thus, that both conventional and Islamic finance will face similar crises in the future if the current system is not fundamentally changed. Currently, Islamic finance is only mimicking the conventional counterparty and its products. As such, it cannot provide a stable and viable alternative to the global financial system until and unless it implements the true spirit of Islamic finance, which requires grassroots changes in the approach to finance in general.

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